

ONLINESHOP.COM: AN E-COMMERCE WEBSITE

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ABSTRACT

The business-to-customer (B2C) aspect of electronic commerce (e-commerce) is the current most visible business use of the World Wide Web (WWW). The main target of an e-commerce web site is to sell products and various services online. Corporate sections and household individuals of the country require different products to fulfill their day by day needs. For that reason they have to go to the shops for fulfilling their needs physically in long and time consuming process. There is also a chance of not getting their desired product in that specific shop, region or country as there is no way to know whether the product or service is available in users region or not. This project tries to come out with successful outcomes of this shortcoming by developing an e-commerce web site for online product sale. The users, in this web site will be providing a producer category to choose from his/her needs. In order to easy the process, a shopping cart is provided to the web registered users who will be able to buy products from the product list and also take shipments of the product just being in his current location thought his/her pc using the Internet. This paper provides an in depth description of the system from an implementation point of view.

Keywords: Business-to-business (B2B), business-to-consumer (B2C), e-commerce, world wide web (WWW).

INTRODUCTION

Online shopping or online retailing is a form of electronic commerce which allows consumers to directly buy goods or services from a seller over the Internet using a web browser. Alternative names are: e-shop, e-store, internet shop, web-shop, web-store, online store, and virtual store. An online shop evokes the physical analogy of buying products or services at a bricks-and-mortar retailer or shopping center; the process is called business-to-consumer (B2C) online shopping. In the case where a business buys from another business, the process is called business-to-business (B2B) online shopping (OS – Online Shopping).

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E-commerce is a fast growing business solution. Many a business organizations are adapting and implementing this new art of business by implementing websites and web solutions providing all the functionalities for choosing and performing commercial transactions over the web. This process is becoming a bigger hit as the days are passing by. Online store is a store on the Internet that has various customers to find out their needed product or service and buy their product of interest. These online shopping applications support the interaction between different parties participating in a commercial transaction via a computer network.

An online catalog of products is maintained in online shopping. Customers can look out through different categories to choose their products from it. The selected products may be collected in a shopping cart. At checkout time, the items in the shopping cart will be represented as an order. At that time, more information will be needed to complete the transaction. Usually the customers will be asked to fill or select a billing address, shipping address, shipping option and payment information. An email notification or message in a mobile will be sent to the customer as soon as the order is placed.

The world is been moving thick and fast these days. People need different things in their day to day life. For that reason they have to go out physically to specific shops and buy their necessary goods there. But problem arises when the products are not available in that shop or region, results in waste of time and money. So that is why we tried to develop such an application that allows the end users to browse a shop just from his mobile and buy and order the placement in his house in a easy navigated process.

This project is titled as 'Online Shop.Com - a cross platform on Online shopping application'. The objective of this project is to develop an e-commerce application for cross platform over the Internet. Online Shop.Com has been engineered for two types of people:

- In Customer end, users will be able to see a home tab. There will four other tabs naming Product, Contact, Terms and Condition, and About Us. Customers can browse products throughout the marketplace using different categories. On logging into the application customers will be able to browse different products in our different categories and add or remove products in the cart. After completing these actions he will be able to pursue the payment process that is done by checking out. His credit information will be

asked to complete the payment process and then the shipment will be processed. In this way customer can browse our application.

- In Salesman end, salesman will have the opportunity to maintain his shop products by adding tags, price and all the other pieces of information he needs to promote his product from his Computer using the Internet. Salesman can add products where he feels the necessity.

LITERATURE OVERVIEW

This section discusses about the background study for the project. To make the project fruitful, we need to study online shopping procedure and the way to attract the end users. Then study on the payment method and the available e-commerce application testing is done. Some limitations of the existing applications are found, which are tried to make up by this project.

E-COMMERCE

Electronic commerce or e-commerce is a term for any type of business, or commercial transaction that involves the transfer of information across the Internet. It covers a range of different types of businesses, from consumer based retail sites, through auction or music sites, to business exchanges trading goods and services between corporations. It is currently one of the most important aspects of the Internet to emerge (WIE – What Is E-commerce).

TYPES OF ECOMMERCE

There are basically four types of E-commerce business in the world now. They are:

1. B2B (Business-to-Business)
2. B2C (Business-to-Client)
3. C2B (Client-to-Business)
4. C2C (Client-to-Client) (ED – E-commerce Definition)

E-COMMERCE IN DIFFERENT STORES IN BANGLADESH

Bangladesh is a developing country. It is also getting used to with newer technologies available in the world. A very few segments of the Bangladeshi business community have used these technology with reasonable success. The introduction of personal computers and internet are also emerging as day-to-day business tools. These positive indicators are favoring the prospects of e-commerce in Bangladesh (AOEIB – Assignment On E-commerce In Bangladesh).

REVIEW OF IMPLEMENTATION STAGE OF E-COMMERCE IN BANGLADESH

The Bangladesh government is now taking necessary steps to build up an e-commerce infrastructure in Bangladesh to cope up with the fast moving world.

- All the banks in Bangladesh are performing non-financial Transactions among them for quite some time now.
- Ministry of Information and Communication Technology is working for enacting a law regarding "Electronic Transaction Act".

WORK FLOW OF THE PROJECT

This section focuses on various working steps of our chosen software process model i.e. Spiral Process Model to engineer our destined e-commerce application. We will demonstrate different steps and our works following the phases of the model to engineer our application.

PLANNING

For the sake of the application a proper planning is needed to get the application done in a good time. While planning of the project we first find out the requirements of the application. So we started planning by starting the following analysis of the work:

- 1) System Requirements Analysis
- 2) Documenting and Analyzing Requirements
- 3) Use Case Analysis
- 4) Data Flow Model
- 5) Data Modeling

1) SYSTEM REQUIREMENTS ANALYSIS

It is the description of the needs and desires for an information system. A requirement describes functions, features and constraints. System requirements define the services provided by the system and prescribe constraints for its operation. Requirements are categorized into functional and nonfunctional. We list below the requirement of the current system in each category as identified.

A) FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENTS

It is a function of feature that must be included in an information system to satisfy the business need and be accepted to the users. We defined the following functional requirements:

- Online product ordering
- Automated memo generation of the transaction
- Reliable and secure transaction policy

B) NONFUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENTS

It is a description of the features, characteristics and attributes of the system as well as any constraints that may limit the boundaries of the proposed solution. We considered the following nonfunctional requirements:

- Performance requirements : throughput rate, response time, efficiency
- Information requirements : inputs and outputs, required data to be stored
- Service requirements : users of different types, training materials

2) DOCUMENTING AND ANALYZING REQUIREMENTS

Information is assembled or documented in an organized, understandable and meaningful way. Various tools to document the initial findings are used in draft form. We used use-cases to describe the system functions from the perspective of external users and in the manner and terminology in which they understand. The use-case diagram of our project has been provided in the latter section.

3) USE CASE ANALYSIS

Use case analysis is the process of identifying and modeling business events, who initiated them and how the system responds to them (UCA – Use Case Analysis). It identifies and describes the system functions from the perspective of the external users using a tool called use cases.

A use case is behaviorally related sequence of steps (scenario), both automated and manual, for the purpose of completing a single business task. It describes the system functions from the perspective of external users and in the manner and terminology in which they understand. To accurately accomplish this demands a high level of user environment. Fig. 1 shows the use case diagram for the project.

For this project, there are three actors: unregistered user, registered user and administrator. For each use case, we listed the following:

- Actor
- Event
- Input or trigger
- All outputs and responses

Fig. 1: Use Case Diagram.

4) DATA FLOW MODEL

A data flow model is a graphical representation of the flow of data through an information system. It can also be used for the visualization of data processing. Here data items flow from an external data sink, via an internal process. It provides no information about the timing or ordering of process or about whether process will operate in sequence or in parallel (DFM – Data Flow Modeling).

Also we can say the process of identifying, modeling and documenting how data moves around an information system. Data flow modeling examines processes (activities that transform data from one form to another), data stores (the holding areas for data), external entities (what sends data into a system or receives data from a system, and data flows (routes by which data can flow). To implement the project, we have used context-level data flow diagram to show the interaction between the system and external agents which act as data sources and data sinks. The context diagram shows the entire system as a single process and gives no clue as to its internal organization and does not contain any data stores. Fig. 2 shows the data flow model of the application.

Fig. 2: Data Flow Diagram.

5) DATA MODELING

A data model is a conceptual representation of the data structures required by a database. The data model focuses on what data should be stored in the database while the process model deals with how the data is processed. To put this in the context of the relational database, the data model is used to design the relational table.

A) ENTITY RELATIONSHIP (ER) DIAGRAM

An ER model is an abstract way to describe a database. Describing a database usually starts with a relational database, which stores data in tables. Some of the data in these tables point to data in other tables - for instance, your entry in the database could point to several entries for each of the phone numbers that are yours. The ER model would say that you are an entity, and each phone number is an entity, and the relationship between you and the phone numbers is 'has a phone number'. Diagrams created to design these entities and relationships are called entity–relationship diagrams or ER diagrams (ERM – Entity Relationship Model). Fig. 3 shows an ER diagram for the project.

Fig. 3: E-R Diagram.

B) TABLES

For the project, we have developed a relational database model which is the primary data model for commercial data-processing applications. The basic structures of the tables composing the database for the project are shown in the table. Fig. 4, Fig. 5 and Fig.6 show the category table, product table and user table, respectively.

Attribute Name	Type
Category id	Int
Name	Varchar
Description	Varchar

Fig. 4: Category Table.

Attribute Name	Type
Product id	Int
Name	Varchar
Description	Varchar
Unitid	Int
Categoryid	Int
Brandid	Int
Price	Double
Discount	Double
Model	Varchar
Image	Varchar
Stock	Int
Last Update	Datetime
Web Site	Varchar
Color	Varchar

Fig. 5: Product Table.

Attribute Name	Type
User id	Int
User name	Varchar
Password	Varchar
User Type	Varchar

Fig. 6: User Table.

C) SCHEMA DIAGRAM

To implement the project we have used 3 tables. All of them are connected and form a relational database. Fig. 7 sows the relationship between the tables.

Fig. 7: Schema Diagram.

RISK ANALYSIS

Then we looked for the potential risk sectors in our planning. In this project, the session management and transaction maintaining is the place where injection of unwanted activates can be made. We have overcome the risk by masking the server

side programming totally in a server isolating from the native application. So it becomes less obvious to hack the system as login into the application as other user. Transaction security has been maintained by the security protocol of PayPal.

ENGINEERING

The project has been divided into two sections. They are:

- Front end
- Back end

FRONT END DESIGNING

In the front end designing we have used native languages HTML5 and JavaScript for creating the User Interface and interaction with the application database.

BACK END DESIGNING

We have used CSS3, HTML5, Java Script, PHP and database design using MySQL for product showcasing, browsing and category browsing as well as user authentication like login in and out and editing.

CUSTOMER EVALUATION (TESTING)

The engineered code was then tested on the browser (for the framework we used were recommended to use Mozilla Firefox), and tested for different circumstances and checked whether the data was begin fetched properly from the server. In this case we found that the category view was missing from our code and was showing all the products at once and as there is not any customized search option it was troublesome to find out the necessary product and also there was a problem that unregistered users were being able to perform transaction i.e. the login protocol was not performed correctly.

RE-ENGINEERING THE PROCESS

The software process model left us with an erroneous version of application. But having used the phases of this model properly, we were able to watch out all the major and minor problems of the application. So we replanted and iterated all the phases of the spiral model until we get our desired application structure.

DISCUSSION

The demonstration of the project is shown in this section.

HOME PAGE

The interface of the application is very simple and user friendly. On loading the application, the users will be able to see 5 icons naming Home, Product, Contact, Terms and Condition, About Us. Tapping on these buttons will show their respective views. Fig. 8 illustrates the home view of the application. Also have a logo in Online Shop.Com. In the upper right also have a member login and registration menu. There is a search option where a customer searches product using product name, description, model, category etc.

Fig. 8: Home View.

PRODUCT VIEW

This section will first show the categories of the product and then will navigate to the products under those categories. The user can add products to cart by tapping on the "Add to Cart" button. A tiny icon will be there on the top of that icon denoting the number of products in the cart currently. Fig. 9 shows the products which are found after the searching.

Fig. 9: Product Search View.

USER LOGIN

There will be a form for login in and a form for signing up. After login in, the user will be able to see his profile information. The admin will be able to upload new products to the database. Fig. 10 and Fig. 11 show the login view and registration view of the project, respectively.

Fig. 10: Login View.

Fig. 11: Registration View.

CONCLUSION

For the overwhelming demand of e-commerce site, an online shopping in Bangladesh, the system has been developed. Online Shopping are now trendsetters in the modern era. The research targets on local and global market. It can be covering this area and customer organizes their own shops or stores, so that their customers can buy or browse their stores and products via this web site. There is no payment method and people cannot pay their money using any online payment methods. This site is created using only core php language. Extensive database, technical knowledge and experience are required to improve the project.

There are scopes for further improvement and enhancement into the total implemented system. The contents of the application can be healthier by evolving more information and adding new restaurants and locations. Our idea is to develop a version of this app totally in the Bengali language. Profit can also be made from this app by using Google Ad sense. Also we want to add international payment methods as like as PayPal, payza, MasterCard and visa card. We also want to add a payment method using local banking.

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